

Policy analysis of equivalent administrative positions into functional positions, mental readiness and career development of regional secretariat employees, Padang city

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(03), 1123–1130

Publication history: Received on 05 May 2023; revised on 18 June 2023; accepted on 20 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1138>

Abstract

This study aims to determine the policies, mental readiness and career development of employees who equalize administrative positions into the functional positions of the Regional Secretariat of the City of Padang. The type of research used is a qualitative method through a descriptive approach. The technique of collecting information through informants was carried out using the snowball sampling technique, in which the number of informants increased according to the needs of the number of informants interviewed was not limited, but stopped after the problem was answered. This study uses in-depth interviews with informants. The results of the study show that the implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions into functional positions is not optimal, mental readiness in equalizing positions ready not ready must be ready because this is a regulation from the center that must be carried out by the Regions, career development for functional positions equivalence is not clear.

Keywords: Policy; Mental Preparedness; Career Development, Indonesia.

1. Introduction

Bureaucratic reform is a necessity that needs to be met in order to ensure the creation of balanced governance. Bureaucratic Reform consists of & (eight) areas of change which include change management, policy deregulation, Organizational Management and Strengthening Management, Apparatus HR Management, Strengthening Accountability, Strengthening Oversight I and Improving the Quality of Public Services. In realizing good governance, reform and changes to the government administration system are needed. Good governance tab is a form of bureaucratic reform that is being promoted by the Government

In order to realize effective governance, the Central Government has issued a bureaucratic simplification policy by issuing Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 17 of 2021 concerning Equalization of Administrative Positions into functional positions which is a follow-up to Permenpan number 28 of 2019 regarding equalization administrative positions into functional positions One of these policies is implemented through the equalization of Administrative Positions (JA) to Functional Positions (1) According to law number 5 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) states that administrative positions are a group of functional positions and tasks related to public services as well as government administration and development while a functional position is a group of positions that contain functions and tasks related to functional services based on certain expertise and skills.

In the equalization of positions, the proposed positions are positions that are affected (deleted) in the simplification of the bureaucracy Equalization of positions is carried out with the following criteria: (1) duties and functions of positions related to functional technical services (2) duties and functions of positions can be carried out by functional officials, (

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3) positions based on certain expertise/skills. The Government of the City of Padang has carried out the direction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia and the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia number 17 of 2021, the Government of the City of Padang has appointed administrative positions to functional positions through a mechanism for equalizing positions within the Padang City Government as many as 317 people . Specifically for the Regional Secretariat, 30 people have been equalized for supervisory positions into functional positions. Currently the functional positions that are equalized still carry out basic tasks and functions as the old structural positions and still serve as Activity Technical Implementation Officers (PPIK) in each Section of the Padang City Regional Secretariat. With the equalization of positions, it causes confusion and anxiety for officials at The city of Padang, both administrators and supervisors, as well as supervisory officials in the Kou Padang Regional Secretariat, because there are no clear policy rules for career development with unclear leads, as well as mental well-being and officials who have had staff/executors so far. Usually officials

supervisors at the Regional Secretariat of the City of Padang have staff under them who will assist in carrying out their main tasks and functions. In psychology, it is known as Post-Power Syndrome, a sign of a person's mental instability that occurs within him after losing his position. Losing a position is not something that can be done on the grounds that until now structural positions are still considered valuable positions or have subordinates (staff). The psychological impact of losing one's position affects one's personality with the assumption that work is an important source of that individual's character. So that someone who experiences a loss of position becomes insecure and social relations become not good. Apart from mental readiness, the question for officials who are equalized is how to get credit points, how to get promoted and how to develop their career in the future (because so far there is still an understanding that career development for civil servants is only in structural positions), is it possible for them to get the same right to be promoted or transferred to another OPD.

In this equalization of positions. The equalized functional must be able to work independently in accordance with the items of activity and by still doing the job as the supervisory official who previously equalized positions in the city of Padang referring to the pattern recommended by the Ministry

Utilization of the State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia with 4 models, so there are still supervisory officials who are retained in accordance with the circular of the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia number B467/KT.01/2021 dated 27 May 2021.

Previous research was conducted by Lia Pitrianingrum, sister (2020) looking at career development in functional positions from the results of equalizing administrative positions: analysis of implementation and challenges with the result that the implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions to functional positions is still not optimal.

The problems raised in this study are how the policy of equalizing administrative positions into functional positions, how is the mental readiness of employees to equalize administrative positions into functional positions, how is the career development of employees who are equalizing administrative positions into functional positions

The purpose of this study is to determine the policy of equalizing administrative positions into functional positions, to find out the mental readiness of employees to equalize administrative positions into functional positions, and to find out the career development of employees for equalizing administrative positions into functional positions at the Padang City Regional Secretariat.

2. Review of literature Equality of Office

Equalization of crimes is the appointment of administrative officials into functional positions through adjustments to the inpassing of functional crimes which are equivalent to Permenpan 17 of 2021. The proposed positions in the equalization of positions are affected crimes removed in bureaucratic simplification. The officials proposed for equalization of positions are administrative officials who, during the simplification of the bureaucracy, sit in positions that are affected (deleted) in the simplification of the bureaucracy.

2.1. Policy

The term policy or wisdom has many meanings. Hogwood and Gunn, as quoted by Parsons (2005:15) mention 10 uses of the term policy, namely (1) as a label for a field of activity, (2) as an expression of general goals or expected state activities, (3) as a specific proposal (4) as a government decision, (5) as a formal authorization, (6) as a program, (7) as output, (8) as an outcome. (9) as a theory or model, and (10) as a process. The modern meaning of the idea of policy

in English is a set of actions or plans that contain political goals. Policy involves behavior as well as intent, it can be action and non-action. Policy refers to a series of actions that aim to have outcomes in the future. Memurur Anderson, 2002 policy as a series of actions taken by actors or a number of actors related to the problems faced by policies related to actions

2.2. Mental Readiness

In the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KKBI), mentality is concerned with the mind and human nature, which are not bodily or energetic. This means that mental is something that cannot be seen or seen directly by the eye which is closely related to the human mind and mind. Thus, mental are things related to psycho or psychology that can be affect individual behavior. A mentally healthy person will not quickly become discouraged, pessimistic or apathetic, because he can face all obstacles or failures in life calmly and naturally and accept failure as a lesson that will lead to success later.

Currently, mentally healthy individuals can be defined in two ways, negatively by the absence of mental disorders and positively when the characteristics of mentally healthy individuals are present. The characteristics of mentally healthy individuals refer to positive conditions or traits such as positive psychological well-being, strong character and virtues (Loenthal, 2006).

2.3. Career Development According to the Law

Republic of Indonesia number 5 of 2014 concerning the State civil apparatus states that civil servant career development is carried out based on: (1) qualifications (2) competence (3) performance appraisal, and (4) the needs of government agencies by considering integrity and morality. So the career development of each civil servant must make a career development plan starting from CPNS until later

The PNS retires According to Samsudin in Kadrisman (2013 334) suggests that career development is a condition which indicates an increase in a person's status in an organization on a predetermined career path in the organization concerned. In addition, Siagian (2005-206) states that whether a person advances or not in his career depends on the person concerned himself, he needs to be actively involved in determining the direction of his career. progress in his career based on a certain career plan But even without planning there are people who achieve progress in his career so that progress is associated with good luck. Regardless of whether fate is rightly associated with one's career, what is clear is that work performance, experience, training and development play an important role in pursuing various career paths that a person can take. Prof. on the opportunity for a worker to obtain the position he hopes or aspires to.

3. Research methods

3.1. Research Informants

Informants are research subjects who can provide information about the phenomenon of the problems raised in the research. Key informants (key informants) are those who know and have various basic information needed in the research. The key informants are the Head of the Organizational Section of the Regional Secretariat of Padang City. The informants in this study are the Head of the BKPSDM Apparatus Development Division and expert policy analysts of the Padang City Regional Secretariat.

Data Collection Techniques The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained or captured in the field through interviews with informants. While secondary data is obtained or collected by people who conduct research from existing sources. Secondary data includes Perwako Tupoksi Regional Secretariat, publications, data on websites or other data that supports this research.

Data collection techniques through interviews with documentary informants. as well as Data Analysis Techniques In this study the authors used descriptive analysis techniques, namely analytical methods that tend to use words to explain the phenomena or data obtained. Data analysis used in this study is data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions or verification.

4. Results study discussion

4.1. Equal Position Policy

Based on the Regulation of the Minister for Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform number 25 of 2021 concerning simplification of the organizational structure in government agencies for simplification of the bureaucracy in article 4 it states that simplification of the bureaucracy is carried out through stages namely simplification of the organizational structure, equalization of descriptions and adjustment of the work system the policy of equalizing administrative descriptions into functional positions is a follow-up to the president's direction in cutting the structure or series of bureaucratic simplifications to 2 levels only, this aims to achieve bureaucratic reform so that the performance of government agencies is no longer rigid but can be agile (agile) in the sense that line positions of personnel intersect filling in, cooperating with each other without being compartmentalized anymore by the structure that has so far been owned. So with this instruction, the Regional Government must carry out and appoint all administrator/supervisory positions currently occupying structural positions regardless of rank, position, competence and education.

The policy for equalizing positions issued by the Central Government is quite good because this will cut/shorten the bureaucracy so that the bureaucracy is more agile (agile), so that services can be quickly implemented. make it easy formerly Head of Department in stages, the current Head of Section can directly coordinate instructing the executor

However, the current obstacle is that the functional equalization of positions is still carrying out its structural duties, has not fully implemented the activity points and collected the credit score, this is because the rules regarding the work system have not been completed. The work system is a series of procedures and work procedures that form a the process of carrying out the activities of carrying out the tasks and functions of the organization's equalization of positions policy is quite good because it cuts/shortens the bureaucracy so that it is more agile, but this equalization policy seems to be forced to implement it for Regional Governments without regard to the needs of the vacancies, competency skills of civil servants and the working period of civil servants who are currently occupying administrator positions. Sean, a civil servant who held the positions of administrator and supervisor, were all appointed as functional equalizers. This raises many problems in the regions, because the rules regarding the work system and the implementation of this policy are not yet clear.

This is what makes the policy of equalizing functional positions confusing because the policy related to the work system has not been completed yet, besides that it also rules out job analysis and workload analysis, whether this functional position is really needed in a Regional Apparatus. all at once, separately so that after the equalization of positions we have to implement regulations related to the work system, where the regulations related to this work system appeared later. This means that the implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions into functional positions is not optimal

4.2. Equal Position Mental Readiness

Equalization of positions can be accepted by some officials at the Padang City Regional Secretariat because in general officials at the Regional Secretariat are used to coordinating and being able to do the work themselves, plus the number of employees who are not too many makes it easier to coordinate so that the emergence of equalization of positions does not become a problem. something new There are also those who are waiting for the equalization of this position because without a competency test it is easy to be appointed directly to a functional position. However, in some Regional Apparatuses there were indeed failures, because they are used to being governed and have staff, with this functional position they are required to work alone. This must be carried out by the Regional Government, because this is a presidential instruction which is followed up by a Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation.functional equalization of these sart positions becomes more productive because they are able to be independent and create new things, competencies that have been hidden so far may emerge because they work on their own initiative both in issuing policies or recommendations in achieving organizational goals

This position assignment policy is in terms of mental readiness that officials who are accustomed to relying on staff in carrying out their duties, will be nervous about dealing with it because automatically the functional positions that will be held will no longer have staff, must work alone and must take the initiative by issuing ideas. new policies, recommendations, or reviewing policies that have been issued. On the other hand, if we look at the functional positions at the Padang City Regional Secretariat, equalization of positions is not a problem, because they are used to coordinating between superiors and subordinates, working in teams and carrying out their own work, regardless of the type of work So for equal functional positions, it's just a matter of adjusting to feeling details of activities according to Permenpan.

What is the problem now is that the equalization of positions is carried out without being supported by an analysis of the existing workload, is it true that each section of the Regional Secretariat must have a functional position and all must be equalized?

Functional positions that are equal from a mental standpoint are not ready in this case because everything is ready and not ready to be carried out because this is a mandate, there will be confusion and there are very many negative assumptions that arise because so far structural officials are in a comfortable period. To maintain psychological equality of functional positions, they are still given the same work space, their income is not reduced, none of the facilities and infrastructure are withdrawn. But unlike the functional positions in the Regional Secretariat, on average they are not too nervous about this policy. they just relax. because the implementation of the duties of each supervisor had previously coordinated well between executors, because the number of employees in each section was not too many, this benefited from the establishment of working groups

4.3. Equal Position PNS Career Development

Based on Law number 5 of 2014 concerning the State civil apparatus, management of civil servant career development is carried out through transfers and or promotions or through special assignments. technical competence, managerial competence and socio-cultural competence. However, in some Regional Apparatuses there were indeed failures, because they are used to being governed and have staff, with this functional position they are required to work alone. This must be carried out by the Regional Government, because this is a presidential instruction which is followed up by a Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation. functional equalization of these sart positions becomes more productive because they are able to be independent and create new things, competencies that have been hidden so far may emerge because they work on their own initiative both in issuing policies or recommendations in achieving organizational goals

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4.4. Equal Position PNS Career Development

Based on Law number 5 of 2014 concerning the State civil apparatus, management of civil servant career development is carried out through transfers and or promotions or through special assignments. technical competence, managerial competence and socio-cultural competence. The rules regarding the implementation of the work of the functional positions are not yet well understood.

For the mental readiness of employees in the equalization of administrative positions into functional positions, namely ready or not ready, they must be ready because these are rules that have been set by the Central Government and must be implemented by the regions, even though in reality there is still confusion/confusion and there are very many built-in assumptions. not positive because so far being a structural official has been in a comfort zone.

In career development, functional positions can be carried out by transferring positions to structural supervisory positions or promotions to administrator positions or senior high leadership positions. However, for career development equalization of functional positions is not clear.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results that have been presented in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that several important things in this study are:

- From a policy point of view, everything is clear, however, there is still a policy on equalization of positions that had not been finalized until then, namely the policy on the work system, where the rules related to this work system appeared later. This means that the implementation of the policy of equalizing administrative positions to functional positions is not optimal yet more in-depth training is provided, specifically for functional positions at the Regional Secretariat, namely the policy analyst functional position. The rules regarding the implementation of the work of the functional positions are not yet well understood.
- For the mental readiness of employees in the equalization of administrative positions into functional positions, namely ready or not ready to be ready because these are rules that have been set by the Central Government and must be carried out by the regions, even though in reality there is still confusion / confusion and there are very built-up assumptions many are not positive because so far being a structural official has been in a comfort zone.
- In career development, functional positions can be carried out by transferring positions/moving to structural supervisory positions or promotion to administrator positions or pratama high leadership positions. However, for career development equalization of functional positions is not clear.

From the results of the above research, some suggestions can be put forward as follows:

- For future researchers, it is hoped that they can examine other variables related to equalization of positions so that they can describe the overall analysis related to equalization of positions.
- It is necessary to design SPBE maturity so that functional positions are mentally ready, this is done by providing adequate allowances, so that an agile work system can be accommodated so that people prefer functional over supervisory positions.
- For functional equalization positions in the City of Padang, it is necessary to develop capacity and capacity in the form of training, outreach or seminars.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We thank the Master of Management STIE KBP as an educational institution.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research.

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